

Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin

D7.5 REPORT ON D&C ACTIVITIES VER 1

**WP7 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION,
RRI, PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT**

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¹ PU= Public, SEN=Sensitive

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CO	Project Coordinator
D	Deliverable
D&C	Dissemination & Communication
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

According to the AquaWind Grant Agreement (GA), every year a report describing the dissemination & communication (D&C) activities carried out and including evaluation indicators will be produced. The present deliverable 'D7.5 Report on D&C activities Ver. 1' is the first release of the three reports on D&C expected to be drafted during the duration of the project.

The deliverable provides an overview of the D&C actions carried out during the first project year following the strategy that had been set up in the AquaWind Dissemination and Communication Plan (D7.1). It also reports the progress of the key performance indicators (KPIs) defined in the GA and in D7.1. The next version of this deliverable is expected in one-year time, at M24.

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1. Introduction

This chapter introduces the scope and aims of the deliverable 'D7.5 Report on D&C activities Ver. 1' developed under Work Package (WP) 7.

1.1 AquaWind dissemination and communication work package

The main objective of WP7 is to disseminate information about the project to a wide audience, including researchers, academics, scientists and technicians, business sector, investors, policy makers and other public and private stakeholders such as fishermen and citizens. This WP is also responsible for carrying out communication activities to promote the visibility of the project itself. WP7 aims to create the tools and framework for effective project communication, awareness and capacity raising, peer exchange and dissemination of results.

This WP responds to all project objectives since it will disseminate and transfer the outputs and results of all AquaWind activities to its key stakeholders. The specific objectives of this WP are:

- To give visibility to the project and raise awareness among the public on the opportunities provided by multiuse solutions.
- To support stakeholder engagement activities in coordination with WP1, trigger societal acceptance, and support the establishment of a local and European community supportive to marine multi-use solutions.
- To support knowledge transfer e.g., through scientific and non-scientific publications, trainings events.
- To connect with a wide network of EU projects, initiatives to exchange experience and promote R&I activities on multi-use.
- To foster a Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach as well as gender equality.

D&C activities in AquaWind will aim thus at ensuring visibility of the project but also at triggering effective interactions with stakeholders at the many project's interfaces. D&C activities are implemented through a set of tasks as defined in the project GA:

Table 1. WP7 tasks' descriptions

Task title	Task description
7.1 Development of the D&C Plan	This task deals with the development and periodic update of the project D&C Plan detailing target groups, communication

	channels, outputs and providing an initial calendar of D&C activities.
7.2 Creation of D&C products and materials	This task deals with the production of several materials and tools including the project website, logo and corporate image, layout, posters and roll-ups as well as banners for social media, and three videos.
7.3 Organisation of events, webinars, workshops, trainings	This task deals with the organisation of (and attendance to) different events, each of one targeting a specific type of stakeholders.
7.4 Synergies with other funded projects	This task deals with establishing relations with other funded projects to foster synergies in knowledge transfer and in exploitation of AquaWind.
7.5 Monitoring and evaluation of Dissemination and Communication activities	Reporting on D&C activities will be performed to measure efforts and results obtained and modify the D&C plan accordingly.
7.6 Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)	This task foresees the creation of a RRI plan for the project leveraging the MUSICA RRI Self-assessment tool.

1.2 Deliverable scope

The aim of **D7.5 Report on D&C activities Ver. 1** is to provide an update on the progress of D&C activities performed by the AquaWind project throughout its first year of life under WP7. The report summarises activities achieved between M1 and M12 (September 2022 - August 2023).

The present deliverable represents the first release of the three reports on D&C that are expected to be drafted throughout the project duration. It is structured around **three main chapters** plus the Executive Summary and the Conclusions:

- *Chapter 1 Introduction:* introducing the scope of the report and presenting the overall approach to D&C set up in the AquaWind D&C Plan at the start of the project.
- *Chapter 2 Update on D&C activities:* describing all D&C activities carried out under WP7 from the beginning of the project until Month 12.
- *Chapter 3 Indicators' monitoring:* providing an overview of the progress of the project towards the D&C indicators defined in the GA and in the D&C Plan.

The deliverable will be updated throughout the project lifecycle: new versions are expected at M24 and at M36.

1.2 Synergies with other Work Packages

WP7 shall work in close **synergy** with **WP1** and, later on, **WP5**. WP1 is in charge of stakeholder planning (task 1.3) and stakeholder engagement activities (task 1.4), while WP5 will foster and maximise the exploitation opportunities of the AquaWind multi-use solution. In particular, at the project start, a mapping of stakeholders of the quadruple helix (task 1.3) has been carried out with the aim of ensuring a wide representation of target groups in the project. The deliverable “D1.3 Stakeholder Engagement Plan”, submitted at M6 (February 2023), has been a key reference guide for the planning and implementation of D&C actions under WP7.

1.3 Target groups

As discussed above, preliminary deliverables and desk research under WP1 and WP7 have defined the main target groups of D&C activities and stakeholder engagement activities. The groups of stakeholders are described below and have been the target of the D&C actions that have been implemented so far and are reported in the present deliverable.

Table 2. Target groups description

Target group	Description
Research community (researchers, PhD students)	Science stakeholders include a diverse network of actors managing, coordinating, or conducting scientific research related to marine activities. This group includes the research community, science managers as well students and PhD scientists. The science category includes actors at local, national, intergovernmental, and European levels as well as representatives of other EU projects.
Industry Representatives, Investors	This category includes representatives of the fishery sector, aquaculture, renewable energy but also maritime transport. In particular companies willing to commercialise the products and services developed in the demo work packages will require robust exploitation plans, risk and benefit assessments, which will be produced under WP5. They will also benefit from the networking opportunities and communication activities offered under WP7.
Societal Actors (citizens, public, civil society organisations)	This category includes both citizens and organisations that operate in the marine field and are affected by marine related activities and citizens who have no specific knowledge of multi-use projects and are not affected by marine activities in their everyday life.

Fisheries communities	The fisheries communities are part of the societal actors but are also a key target group on its own. Due to the nature of the project, combining not only offshore wind energy that might interfere with fisheries space and the fishes itself but with the aquaculture part might pose a threat to the artisanal ways of fishing in the islands. For this reason, many activities for WP1, task 1.3 and task 1.4 consider this target group in specific.
Policy and decision-makers	This group will require short and concise recommendations and visual documentation facilitating the understanding of how marine multi-use projects can impact a broader policy sector and how policy can support or hamper their implementation. Policymakers at regional, national and EU level will be targeted.

Following the definition of the key project target groups, core D&C channels and type of information to be shared with each stakeholder group has been defined in D7.1. The D&C activities reported in this deliverable have been carried out following this approach.

Table 3. Target groups communication details

Target group	Communication channels	Type of information
Research community (researchers, PhD students)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project results 	
Industry Representatives, Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business/exploitation plan 	
Societal Actors (citizens, public, civil society organisations) + Fisheries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project impact assessment 	
Policy and decision-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advantages of the prototype 	

2. Update on dissemination & communication activities

This chapter reports on the D&C activities implemented throughout the first project year in line with the D&C Plan and the GA.

2.1 Visual identity and information materials

AquaWind has developed a dedicated visual identity for an efficient dissemination of the results of the project. The first and central element to develop in order to have a consistent visual identity is the logo and the main colours and style that have been used – and will continue to be used - in D&C materials and all other documents of the project, thus defining the project’s identity and ensuring recognisability.

The logo in Figure 1 was developed by the WP leader CE with the feedback and suggestions of all partners. To develop the logo, the two main elements of the multi-use solution: Aquaculture and Off-shore wind energy were given special importance being represented by the windmills and the fish. Another element of special importance is the Circular economy which is represented by the circle closing the design.

Figure 1. AquaWind's logotype

Figure 2. AquaWind's colours and typography

Main typography

Myriad Pro Regular AaBbCcDdEeFfGg
 Myriad Pro Condensed AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKk
 Myriad Pro Condensed Italic AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJj
 Myriad Pro Light AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIi
 Myriad Pro Semibold AaBbCcDdEe
 Myriad Pro Semibold Italic AaBbCcDdEe
 Myriad Pro Bold Condensed AaBbCcDdEeFfGg
 Myriad Pro Bold AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
 Myriad Pro Bold Italic AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz

Secondary typography

Calibri

Designer: Luc(as) De Groot

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1234567890~!@#%&^*(){}|'"/>

The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog.

The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog.

The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog.

Following the developed visual identity, initial information and promotional materials have been developed. These include:

Leaflet and poster

The AquaWind project created a comprehensive leaflet during its initial months, which encompasses essential information about the project. In addition, the leaflet has been designed to adapt to various attended events, ensuring that the content is tailored to effectively reach the project's specific target groups. General information about the project has been incorporated into the leaflet, ensuring that it serves as a valuable resource for disseminating key project details and engaging with stakeholders across different events about its prototyping and offshore renewable energy combined with aquaculture.

Figure 3. Example of AquaWind's Leaflet/Poster

Roll-up

A designed roll-up banner measuring 85cm x 200cm has been developed for AquaWind. This promotional material has been strategically distributed to partners for use during various D&C activities. In particular, the roll-up banner has been prominently displayed at different events, helping to raise awareness and generate interest among attendees.

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Figure 4. AquaWind's Roll-up

 Other templates

In addition, templates for banners, project documents, deliverables, Power Point presentations, etc have been developed following the established visual identity.

Figure 5. AquaWind's corporate templates

2.2 Website

The **AquaWind website** is a dynamic platform that undergoes continuous updates and enhancements to engage a broad audience of international and EU stakeholders. Serving as a comprehensive window, the website showcases various digital elements, news, and events associated with the project, establishing itself as a primary tool for effectively communicating not just the message, but also the purpose of AquaWind to the public. The initial version of the website was created during the project's early stages, as documented in D7.1 of the Dissemination and Communication Plan submitted in M3. Since then, consistent efforts have been made to improve the website's design, structure, and activity tracking. As a result, it has evolved significantly, aligning with the evolving needs of its users:

- To increase accessibility and reading, the website has experimented adjustments to its design.
- The website site map has been updated to increase indexability, and new events have been added.
- A Google Analytics tag has been inserted on the website to measure visits under Global site tag: UA-254230170-1 (gtag.js).
- The Cookies Policy has been put to the footer section in a prominent location. The website displays a pop-up window informing and requesting consent from visitors regarding their GDPR compliance options.

As an ever-evolving platform, this document will be regularly updated to accommodate the ongoing progress of the project and to address emerging needs and information that require sharing and dissemination. The latest version of the website can be accessed at the following address: <https://aquawind.eu/>

Below, a preview of its refreshed design can be found.

Figure 6. Website's preview

Website insights

The following insights show the overall data in terms of statistics and interactions with the project’s website since its launch at the earliest stage of the project²:

Figure 7. Website’s analytics

Since the establishment of the project website in M5, AquaWind has acquired a total of **1,578 visitors** and approximately **4,890 page views** counting the different pages inside the platform and **1,821 visits**.

Visitor countries

Figure 8. World’s ranking of visitors

Analysis of the top 10 visitor countries reveals that AquaWind predominantly garners visits from Spanish and Irish audience since the website's launch, followed by United States, France and Portugal.

Website articles

The AquaWind project has taken significant efforts to inform and engage stakeholders by publishing a diverse range of articles on its website. These articles aim to provide up-to-date news and updates regarding the project. To facilitate easy access, a table has been included below, listing the articles along with their corresponding links. This

² Data analytics as of 23rd August 2023.

comprehensive approach ensures that stakeholders are well-informed and can easily access the information they seek.

The list of articles drafted by WP7 Leader CE and published on the website is provided in Table 4 below. In addition, Table 5 shows the articles about AquaWind published by the project partners on their own website.

Table 4. List of AquaWind's website articles

Date	Title	Link
14/10/2022	Gran Canaria leads the pioneering AquaWind project to merge wind power and aquaculture	https://aquawind.eu/2022/10/14/gran-canaria-leads-the-pioneering-aquawind-project-to-merge-wind-power-and-aquaculture/
28/10/2022	Offshore wind power and fishing sector conference in the Canary Islands	https://aquawind.eu/2022/10/28/offshore-wind-power-and-fishing-sector-conference-in-the-canary-islands/
18/11/2022	The AquaWind project will be present at the XVIII Spanish National Congress of Aquaculture	https://aquawind.eu/2022/11/18/the-aquawind-project-will-be-present-at-the-xviii-spanish-national-congress-of-aquaculture/
24/11/2022	AquaWind surprises at the Cádiz National Aquaculture Congress	https://aquawind.eu/2022/11/24/aquawind-surprises-at-the-cadiz-national-aquaculture-congress/
13/12/2022	Spain will receive €1.12 billion from the EMFAF 2021-2027	https://aquawind.eu/2022/12/13/spain-will-receive-e1-12-billion-from-the-emfaf-2021-2027/
21/02/2023	Latest EU policy measures for more sustainable fisheries, aquaculture and marine ecosystems	https://aquawind.eu/2023/02/21/latest-eu-policy-measures-for-more-sustainable-fisheries-aquaculture-and-marine-ecosystems/
28/3/2023	AquaFuture Spain receives the AquaWind project during its first day	https://aquawind.eu/2023/03/28/aquafuture-spain-receives-the-aquawind-project-during-its-first-day/
28/04/2023	European Maritime Day 2023	https://aquawind.eu/2023/04/28/european-maritime-day-2023/
24/05/2024	An historic achievement: Treaty of the High Seas is adopted	https://aquawind.eu/2023/05/24/an-historic-achievement-treaty-of-the-high-seas-is-adopted/
31/05/2023	The EU Blue Economy Report 2023	https://aquawind.eu/2023/05/30/the-eu-blue-economy-report-2023/
01/06/23	AquaWind meets its sister project FLORA	https://aquawind.eu/2023/06/01/aquawind-meets-its-sister-project-flora/

28/06/2023	First public results of AquaWind	https://aquawind.eu/2023/06/28/first-public-results-of-aquawind/
13/07/2023	AquaWind at FIMAR 2023	https://aquawind.eu/2023/07/13/aquawind-at-fimar-2023/
02/08/2023	Sustainable fishing in the EU: state of play and orientations for 2024	https://aquawind.eu/2023/08/02/sustainable-fishing-in-the-eu-state-of-play-and-orientations-for-2024/
08/08/2023	EC Launches Consultation for Energy Transition Partnership in EU Fisheries and Aquaculture Sector	https://aquawind.eu/2023/08/08/ec-launches-consultation-for-energy-transition-partnership-in-eu-fisheries-and-aquaculture-sector/
16/08/2023	EU's Progress Towards UN Sustainable Development Goals: A Mixed Bag for "Life Below Water"	https://aquawind.eu/2023/08/16/eus-progress-towards-un-sustainable-development-goals-a-mixed-bag-for-life-below-water/
23/08/2023	Commissioner Sinkevičius Calls for Action to Improve Baltic Sea Environment	https://aquawind.eu/2023/08/23/commissioner-sinkevicius-calls-for-action-to-improve-baltic-sea-environment/

Table 5. List of AquaWind articles published on project partners' websites

Date	Partner	Title	Link
09/2023	GOBCAN-ACIISI	AquaWind project	https://www.gobiernodecanarias.org/convocatorias/temas/investigacion/proyectos/2020/
09/2023	WavEC	AquaWind project	https://www.wavec.org/en/research-development/projects/aquawind
7/10/2022	ULPGC	ARRANCA EL PROYECTO EUROPEO AQUAWIND	https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/en/noticias/item/703-arranca-el-proyecto-europeo-aquawind.html
10/10/2022	CMC	KICK OFF Meeting Proyecto Aquawind	https://www.clustermc.es/kick-off-meeting-proyecto-aquawind/
11/10/2022	PLOCAN	Lanzamiento del proyecto europeo Aquawind de energía eólica y acuicultura offshore que coordina la ACIISI	https://www.plocan.eu/lanzamiento-del-proyecto-europeo-aquawind-de-energia-eolica-y-acuicultura-offshore-que-coordina-la-aciisi/
11/10/2022	CE	Gran Canaria leads the pioneering AquaWind project to merge wind power and aquaculture	https://consulta-europa.com/gran-canaria-leads-the-pioneering-aquawind-project-to-merge-wind-power-and-aquaculture/

14/10/2022	CMC	Encuentro de la eólica marina con el sector pesquero en Canarias	https://www.clustermc.es/encuentro-de-la-eolica-marina-con-el-sector-pesquero-en-canarias/
25/10/2022	ULPGC	La Vicerrectora de Investigación Marisol Izquierdo acude a la Jornada de Energía Eólica Marina	https://www.ulpgc.es/noticia/2022/10/25/vicerrectora-investigacion-marisol-izquierdo-acude-jornada-energia-eolica-marina
27/10/2022	CMC	La eólica marina y el sector pesquero apuestan por la convivencia	https://www.clustermc.es/la-eolica-marina-offshore-y-el-sector-pesquero-apuestan-por-la-convivencia/
28/10/2022	CMC	Canarias lidera el proyecto AquaWind para fusionar energía eólica y acuicultura	https://www.clustermc.es/canarias-lidera-el-proyecto-aquawind-para-fusionar-energia-eolica-y-acuicultura/
24/11/2022	ULPGC - FPCT, CMC	AquaWind sorprende en el Congreso Nacional de Acuicultura de Cádiz	https://www.ecoaqua.eu/es/blog/aquawind-sorprende-en-el-congreso-nacional-de-acuicultura-de-cadiz-a3542.html ; https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/es/noticias/item/717-aquawind-sorprende-en-el-congreso-nacional-de-acuicultura-de-cadiz.html ; https://www.clustermc.es/aquawind-sorprende-en-el-congreso-nacional-de-acuicultura-de-cadiz/
25/11/2022	ULPGC	Presentado el proyecto AquaWind en el Congreso Nacional de Acuicultura de Cádiz	https://www.ulpgc.es/noticia/2022/11/25/presentado-proyecto-aquawind-congreso-nacional-acuicultura-cadiz
25/11/2022	CE	AquaWind surprises at the Cádiz National Aquaculture Congress	https://consulta-europa.com/aquawind-surprises-at-the-cadiz-national-aquaculture-congress/
31/03/2023	CMC	El Proyecto Aquawind presente en Aquafuture Spain	https://www.clustermc.es/el-proyecto-aquawind-presente-en-aquafuture-spain/
31/03/2023	CE	Consulta Europa attends AquaFuture Spain event with AquaWind project	https://consulta-europa.com/consulta-europa-attends-aquafuture-spain-event-with-aquawind-project/
01/06/2023	PLOCAN	Collaboration of the European projects AquaWind and FLORA that will be tested in PLOCAN	https://plocan.eu/en/collaboration-of-the-european-projects-aquawind-and-flora-that-will-be-tested-in-plocan
01/06/2023	ULPGC	PROYECTOS EUROPEOS AQUAWIND Y FLORA EXPLORAN	https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/en/noticias/item/780-proyectos-europeos-

		SINERGIAS EN EVENTO CONJUNTO EN GRAN CANARIA	aquawind-y-flora-exploran-sinergias-en-evento-conjunto-en-gran-canaria.html
02/06/2023	CE	AquaWind project explores synergies with FLORA in a joint event in Gran Canaria	https://consulta-europa.com/aquawind-project-explores-synergies-in-a-joint-event-in-gran-canaria/
08/06/2023	CMC	Los proyectos europeos AquaWind y FLORA exploran sinergias en evento conjunto en Gran Canaria	https://www.clustermc.es/los-proyectos-europeos-aquawind-y-flora-exploran-sinergias-en-evento-conjunto-en-gran-canaria/
19/06/2023	CMC	CMC y FEDEPORT dan a conocer las profesiones azules en FIMAR 2023	https://www.clustermc.es/cmc-y-fedeport-dan-a-conocer-las-profesiones-azules-en-fimar-2023/
03/07/2023	CE	First public results of AquaWind project	https://consulta-europa.com/first-public-results-of-aquawind-project/

Last but not least, it can be highlighted that the AquaWind project has been featured on the CINEA website:

Table 6. AquaWind articles published on CINEA website.

Date	Title	Link
11/07/2023	AQUAWIND - Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/featured-projects/aquawind-innovative-multi-use-prototype-combining-offshore-renewable-energy-and-aquaculture-atlantic_en
24/07/2023	Promoting the sustainable blue economy: EMFAF Flagship call 2021 projects – a year on	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/promoting-sustainable-blue-economy-emfaf-flagship-call-2021-projects-year-2023-07-24_en

2.3 Social media

For communication purposes a set of social media accounts has been established, each targeting different audiences. These accounts are regularly updated providing valuable information on project results, partner updates, organised events, interviews, and other relevant project-related activities. The social media channels serve as dynamic platforms for sharing up-to-date information, engaging with stakeholders, and promoting awareness about the project. The AquaWind project ensures widespread communication of project updates and facilitates active participation and interaction with interested individuals and organisations.

The following table shows a general view about the performance on each channel from October 2022 (M2) until August 2023 (M12):

Table 7. Social media channels

Channels	Link	Nº posts	Followers
	AquaWind Project https://www.linkedin.com/in/aquawind-project-9b321b247/	52	272
	@aquawindproject https://www.instagram.com/aquawindproject/	23	462
	AquaWind Project https://www.facebook.com/aquawind.eu	49	80
	@AquawindP https://twitter.com/AquawindP	62	135

Social Media Insights³

LinkedIn

The LinkedIn account has demonstrated excellent content performance, garnering a **remarkable 16,107 impressions**. This high number of impressions showcases the effectiveness of AquaWind's content strategy in capturing attention, generating interest and fostering meaningful engagement with the project's target audience. Through its LinkedIn presence, AquaWind has been able to establish an initial strong digital footprint, starting to cultivate valuable connections within the industry and the research community.

³ Data analytics as of 23rd August 2023.

Figure 9. Content performance

 Facebook

Aquawind's Facebook account has experienced good engagement with a following of 80 individuals and a reach of over **13,700 impressions**. This demonstrates the growing interest and visibility of the project among Facebook users. The account has effectively utilised this platform to disseminate project updates, share relevant content, and engage with stakeholders and the wider online community.

Figure 10. Facebook Growth

 Instagram

The AquaWind project has also maintained an active presence on Instagram, where its official account has attained so far an outreach of **6,000 impressions** over the past year. Through engaging content and regular updates, AquaWind has effectively utilised Instagram to communicate and disseminate the project.

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Figure 11. Instagram Growth

 Twitter/X

AquaWind's Twitter/X account has been actively engaging with its audience over the past year, garnering increasing traction and interaction. With 135 followers, 67 likes and 31 retweets from a total of 62 tweets, AquaWind has successfully captured the attention and interest of its followers.

Figure 12. Twitter Interactions

2.4 Newsletter

To ensure effective dissemination of project updates and achievements, the AquaWind newsletter serves as a valuable communication tool. It provides regular updates on project activities, highlights latest developments, and promotes awareness of the project and its advancements.

The **first newsletter has been released in February 2023 and distributed to 108 recipients.** This tool plays an important role generating interest and engagement among stakeholders promoting the vision of integrating marine renewable energy production and finfish aquaculture in the Atlantic region.

The newsletter design was developed according to the visual identity, and it is written and available in English for download from the AquaWind [website](#).

Figure 13. First newsletter release

Continuous efforts are made to promote newsletter's subscriptions via the website, the social media, and when organising events and other stakeholder engagement activities. To date, the project has reached 155 newsletter subscribers. The next newsletter release is programmed in September 2023 in conjunction with the launch of the WP1 pre-demonstration survey and the start of the promotional campaign for the first project video.

2.5 Press releases

Project partners have already made significant progress in the development of press releases by showcasing AquaWind to a wider audience and creating greater awareness of the project and its goals. With a total of **36 press releases generated thus far**, they have emerged as a vital component for increasing visibility and engagement.

To date, there have been 19 national press releases, aimed at disseminating project updates and achievements within partners countries. Additionally, the project has reached a broader audience with 4 international press releases, highlighting its global significance and impact. Moreover, the project's regional impact is emphasised through 13 regional press releases, including three radio appearances and one in a prominent paper magazine, targeting specific geographical areas to raise awareness and foster local engagement.

Table 8. Press release list

Date	Title	Media	Type of media	Dissemination level	Link
Project launch & kick off meeting					
1/7/2022	EMFAF flagship projects on regional maritime cooperation kick off	CINEA	ONLINE PRESS	INTERNATIONAL	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/emfaf-flagship-projects-regional-maritime-cooperation-kick-2022-07-01_en
6/7/2022	7 PROYECTOS DEL FEMPA PARA LA COOPERACIÓN MARÍTIMA	Sector Marítimo	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://sectormaritimo.es/7-proyectos-del-fempa-para-la-cooperacion-maritima
8/7/2022	Seven EU funded projects are kicking off to strengthen sea basin-level collaboration in the Atlantic, the Black Sea and the Western Mediterranean.	European office of cyprus	ONLINE PRESS	INTERNATIONAL	https://eoc.org.cy/emfaf-flagship-projects-on-regional-maritime-cooperation-kick-off/
11/10/2022	Arranca el proyecto europeo AquaWind, que une la energía eólica offshore con la acuicultura	IPAC	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	http://www.ipacuicultura.com/noticias/en_portada/82206/arranca_el_proyecto_europeo_aquawind_que_un_e_la_energia_eolica_offshore_con_la_acuicultura.html
11/10/2022	Gran Canaria presenta AquaWind, proyecto pionero que vincula energía eólica y acuicultura	Canarias Noticias	ONLINE PRESS	REGIONAL	https://canariasnoticias.es/2022/10/11/gran-canaria-presenta-aquawind-proyecto-pionero-que-vincula-energia-eolica-y-acuicultura
11/10/2022	Aquawind busca integrar la eólica marina offshore con la acuicultura	INFOPUERTOS	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://infopuertos.com/aquawind-busca-integrar-la-eolica-marina-offshore-con-la-acuicultura/
12/10/2022	Ingenium o cómo posicionar en el sector de los parques eólicos marinos a una región sin acceso al mar	El Español	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://www.elespanol.com/invertia/disruptores-innovadores/autonomias/castilla-la-mancha/20221012/ingenium-posicionar-sector-parques-eolicos-marinos-sin/709929214_0.html
12/10/2022	Gran Canaria presenta un proyecto pionero que vincula energía eólica y acuicultura	SIGLO XXI	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://www.diariosigloxxi.com/texto-diario/mostrar/3923898/gran-canaria-presenta-proyecto-pionero-vincula-energia-eolica-acuicultura
13/10/2022	Canarias acoge pruebas pioneras que combinan	MisPeces	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://www.mispeces.com/noticias/Canarias-acoge-pruebas-pioneras-

	energías eólicas offshore y piscicultura				que-combinan-energias-eolicas-offshore-y-piscicultura/#.Y1---3bP1D8
14/10/2022	Canarias lidera el proyecto pionero AquaWind para fusionar energía eólica y acuicultura	INFOPUERTOS	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://infopuertos.com/canarias-lidera-el-proyecto-pionero-aquawind-para-fusionar-energia-eolica-y-acuicultura/
14/10/2022	Cómo combinar la energía eólica con la acuicultura	EnergyHub	ONLINE PRESS	REGIONAL	http://www.energyhub.es/texto-diario/mostrar/3927225/como-combinar-energia-eolica-acuicultura
26/10/2022	Canarias lidera el proyecto AquaWind para fusionar energía eólica y acuicultura	El Espejo Canario	RADIO	REGIONAL	https://www.elespejocanario.es/secciones/canarias-lidera-el-proyecto-aquawind-para-fusionar-energia-eolica-y-acuicultura/
26/10/2022	Economía Azul	El Espejo Canario	RADIO	REGIONAL	https://www.elespejocanario.es/secciones/canarias-lidera-el-proyecto-aquawind-para-fusionar-energia-eolica-y-acuicultura/
30/09/2022	Protótipo Multiuso Inovador Combina Energía Renovable Offshore e Acuicultura na Bacia do Atlântico	Revista da Marinha	MAGAZINE	NATIONAL	Printed edition - no link
11/10/2022	Arranca el proyecto europeo AquaWind, que une la energía eólica offshore con la acuicultura	OESA	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://www.observatorio-acuicultura.es/comunicacion/actualidad/arranca-el-proyecto-europeo-aquawind-que-une-la-energia-eolica-offshore-con
9/11/2022	Canarias lidera el proyecto AquaWind para fusionar energía eólica y acuicultura	BOLETÍN HONTZA	ONLINE PRESS	REGIONAL	https://plocan.hontza.es/sbes/boletin_report/18/my_web/897
28/11/2022	Magnífica acogida del proyecto AquaWind en el Congreso Nacional de Acuicultura de Cádiz	INFOPUERTOS	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://infopuertos.com/magnifica-acogida-del-proyecto-aquawind-en-el-congreso-nacional-de-acuicultura-de-cadiz/
Local stakeholder engagement events and other project events					
15/10/2022	La convivencia con la pesca centra el debate en las Jornadas de Eólica Marina	La Provincia	ONLINE PRESS	REGIONAL	https://www.laprovincia.es/las-palmas/2022/10/15/convivencia-pesca-centra-debate-jornadas-77268407.html

15/10/2022	Encuentro de la eólica marina con el sector pesquero en Canarias	INFOPUERTOS	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://infopuertos.com/encuentro-de-la-eolica-marina-con-el-sector-pesquero-en-canarias/
19/10/2022	Telde, centro de pruebas para el proyecto europeo AquaWind	TELDEACTUALIDAD	ONLINE PRESS	REGIONAL	https://teldeactualidad.com/art/131815/medioambiente
20/10/2022	La eólica marina busca hacer las paces con la pesca	EnergyHub	ONLINE PRESS	REGIONAL	http://www.energyhub.es/texto-diario/mostrar/3935742/eolica-marina-busca-hacer-paces-pesca
27/10/2022	La eólica marina offshore y el sector pesquero apuestan por la convivencia	INFOPUERTOS	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://infopuertos.com/la-eolica-marina-offshore-y-el-sector-pesquero-apuestan-por-la-convivencia/
27/10/2022	El CMC defiende una eólica marina en convivencia con la biodiversidad	Diario del Puerto	ONLINE PRESS	REGIONAL	https://www.diariodelpuerto.com/maritimo/el-cmc-defiende-una-eolica-marina-en-convivencia-con-la-biodiversidad-ML12808307
25/11/2022	DEBATES DE INGENIERÍA DE LA ENERGÍA. COMBINAR ENERGÍA EÓLICA CON PISCIFACTORÍAS	Inmoley	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://www.inmoley.com/NOTICIAS/2212345/2022-1-inmobiliario-urbanismo-vivienda/011-22-inmobiliario-25-21.html
25/11/2022	AquaWind project makes a splash at Cádiz National Aquaculture Congress	The Fish Site	ONLINE PRESS	INTERNATIONAL	https://thefishsite.com/articles/aquawind-project-makes-a-splash-at-c%C3%A1diz-national-aquaculture-congress
25/11/2022	AquaWind: energías renovables, seguridad alimentaria a través de la acuicultura y crecimiento azul	IPAC Acuicultura	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	http://www.ipacuicultura.com/noticias/en_portada/82525/aquawind_en_energias_renovables_seguridad_alimentaria_a_traves_de_la_acuicultura_y_crecimiento_azul.html
25/11/2022	AquaWind surprises at the Cádiz National Aquaculture Congress	AquaHoy	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://aquahoy.com/aquawind-surprises-at-the-cadiz-national-aquaculture-congress/
25/11/2022	AquaWind sorprende en el Congreso Nacional de Acuicultura de Cádiz	Radio Faro del Noroeste	ONLINE PRESS	REGIONAL	https://www.radiofaronoroeste.es/secciones/nacional/item/11972-aquawind-sorprende-en-el-congreso-nacional-de-acuicultura-de-cadiz
5/6/2023	European projects AquaWind and FLORA explore synergies in a joint event in Gran Canaria	AquaHoy	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://aquahoy.com/proyectos-europeos-aquawind-flora-exploran-sinergias-evento-conjunto-gran-canaria/

5/6/2023	Los proyectos europeos AquaWind y FLORA exploran sinergias	IPACacuicultura	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://www.ipacuicultura.com/noticia.php?id=67589
5/6/2023	Los proyectos europeos AquaWind y FLORA que se ensayarán en PLOCAN establecen las bases para futuras colaboraciones	INFOPUERTOS	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://infopuertos.com/los-proyectos-europeos-aquawind-y-flora-que-se-ensayaran-en-plocan-establecen-las-bases-para-futuras-colaboraciones/
7/6/2023	Plocan acoge el ensayo de los proyectos europeos AquaWind y Flora	ivoox	ONLINE PRESS	NATIONAL	https://www.ivoox.com/plocan-acoge-ensayo-proyectos-europeos-audios-mp3_rf_109919440_1.html
07/06/2023	Plocan acoge el ensayo de los proyectos europeos AquaWind y Flora	El Espejo Canario	RADIO	REGIONAL	https://www.elespejocanario.es/secciones/plocan-acoge-el-ensayo-de-los-proyectos-europeos-aquawind-y-flora/
8/6/2023	La Plocan acoge el ensayo de los proyectos europeos AquaWind y Flora	Energy hub	ONLINE PRESS	REGIONAL	http://www.energyhub.es/texto-diario/mostrar/4326033/plocan-acoge-ensayo-proyectos-europeos-aquawind-flora
9/6/2023	Offshore aquaculture/renewables projects explore synergies	The Fish Site	ONLINE PRESS	INTERNATIONAL	https://thefishsite.com/articles/offshore-aquaculture-renewables-projects-explore-synergies
25/06/2023	El banco de ensayos pone a prueba los prototipos de AquaWind y Flora	TELDEACTUALIDAD	ONLINE PRESS	REGIONAL	https://teldeactualidad.com/art/153702/el-banco-de-ensayos-pone-a-prueba-los-prototipos-de-aquawind-y-flora
7/8/2023	La plataforma flotante del proyecto AquaWind unifica aerogeneradores e instalaciones de acuicultura	SMARTGRIDSINFO	ONLINE PRESS	REGIONAL	https://www.smartgridsinfo.es/2023/08/07/plataforma-flotante-proyecto-aquawind-unifica-aerogeneradores-instalaciones-acuicultura

Within this framework, CE has started to work on press interview collection, as per GA. Press interviews format is defined in the D&C Plan as follows:

- Quotes for strategic communications, web, and social media, to share for the radio and/or podcasts.
- Video. Small video pills for social media, which can also be shared to TV and other media.
- Radio interviews. Promotion mainly through national/regional radios.

In the first year of the project, CE has recollected quotes of partners and other stakeholders for strategic communications and for the creation of press releases. **Three radio interviews** specifically dedicated to AquaWind have also been achieved on a local radio station in collaboration with the partner CMC – Canary Islands’ Maritime Cluster, which considered a particularly positive achievement of D&C actions.

In the next year, CE plans to conduct more work on the production of interview video pills upon the availability of first concrete results emerging from the innovation activities of the W2Power prototype.

2.6 Promotional videos

As per GA, three promotional videos shall be produced by AquaWind as follows:

- A first **animation video** at the beginning of the project to inform about the objectives and vision of it.
- A **demonstration video** of the technological and operational aspects of the AquaWind solution.
- A **storytelling video** involving staff from the project and other stakeholders involved in the project activities.

The videos are to be produced in English with subtitles in the three languages of the Consortium (Spanish, Portuguese, French). These videos shall be uploaded to AquaWind’s YouTube and distributed across partners’ websites and other channels.

The first video has been produced and released at M12 (see D7.2 Videos Ver. 1), with the aim of presenting the overall scope of AquaWind, its objectives, and main activities and results expected from this funding experience.

The video is available on AquaWind [Youtube channel](#) and website’s [homepage](#). On YouTube channel, videos with subtitles in the project languages are also provided.

In September 2023, a dissemination campaign for the video promotion is planned through the newsletter and the social media. Also, project partners will be requested to promote it through their available and most suitable channels.

The production process of the first video involved CE crafting the script and collaborating with partners on its development. Following pre-production, graphic elements were designed, leading to the creation of a captivating video. More information is provided in D7.2.

2.7 Events

Attendance to events

Throughout the past year, partners from the AquaWind consortium actively participated in various events, bolstering the project's promotion and recognition within the scientific community, among policy makers, industry stakeholders, and the general public. These events include the International Ocean Conference on Ocean Energy (ICOE), Congreso Nacional de Acuicultura, InnovAzul - II Encuentro Internacional de Conocimiento y Economía Azul, EMFAF 2022 Info Day, EU Missions - Restore our ocean and waters, AquaFuture, and FIMAR 2023 - Feria Internacional del Mar 2023.

Notable partners who have attended these events and contributed to AquaWind's engagement are EnerOcean, WavEC, GOBCAN, ULPGC, CMC, CE, PLOCAN, CANEXMAR, and ENEROCEAN. Their active participation in these events has played a crucial role in promoting the project, fostering connections with the scientific community, policy makers, industry stakeholders, and the wider public. The following table enlist all the events and its purposes:

Table 9. Attended events by AquaWind Consortium

Partner	Type of event	Target group	Name	Location	Date	Description
EnerOcean, WavEC	Conference participation	Industry; Scientific Community	International Ocean Conference on Ocean Energy (ICOE)	San Sebastián, Spain	18-20 October 2022	Participation in a stand for AquaWind promotion (leaflets handed over).
GOBCAN-ACIISI, ULPGC, CE	Conference participation	Industry; Scientific Community	Congreso Nacional de Acuicultura	Cádiz, Spain	21-24 November 2022	Presentation of AquaWind by the project Coordinator at the conference. In addition, the WP1 survey was distributed among stakeholders at the conference to collect feedback on multi-use pilot projects combining aquaculture with other types of marine activities such as offshore energy.

EnerOcean	Conference participation	Industry; Scientific Community	InnovAzul - II Encuentro Internacional de Conocimiento y Economía Azul	Cádiz, Spain	29-30 November 2022	Participation in a stand for AquaWind promotion (leaflets handed over).
CMC	Conference participation	Policy makers	EMFAF 2022 Info Day	Brussels, Belgium	24 November 2022	Participation in the event and promotion of AquaWind.
CE	Exhibition	Policy Makers; Others	EU Missions - Restore our ocean and waters	Brussels, Belgium	17 February 2023	Involvement in the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters Charter and presentation of AquaWind through a dedicated poster.
All partners	Conference participation	Investors; Industry	AquaFuture	Santiago De Compostela, Spain	28-30 March 2023	Presentation of AquaWind given by Project Coordinator at the conference and in a dedicated stand. Technical meetings with providers for the cage and the feeding system of the AquaWind prototype as well as project meeting among partners that attended the event. In addition, the WP1 survey was distributed among stakeholders at the conference to collect feedback on multi-use energy-aquaculture pilot projects.
CMC	Exhibition	Industry	FIMAR 2023 - Feria Internacional del Mar 2023	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain	16-18 June 2023	Participation in the event with an institutional stand and promotion of AquaWind.

Organisation of events

The AquaWind project has prioritised effective communication and engagement with both the general public and the scientific community. As part of this initiative, two events were organised by AquaWind partners within the past year, and their descriptions are provided in the following paragraphs. These events were specifically designed to foster interaction, disseminate project information, and encourage active participation from a diverse range of stakeholders.

Table 10. Organised events by AquaWind Consortium

Organising partner	Type of event	WP	Target group	Name of the event	Date	Location
CMC organiser (with support of GOBCAN-ACIISI and CE)	Conference	WP1, WP7	Fisheries communities	Jornada de Energía Eólica Marina en Canarias. Proyección y retos (EN: Conference on Offshore Wind Energy in the Canary Islands. Challenges and opportunities)	25 October 2022	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain
CMC and CE organisers. Participation of all partners	Workshop	WP7	Sister project	AQUAWIND-FLORA Joint Event (Sister project)	1 June 2023	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain

Under WP1, the Conference on *Offshore Wind Energy in the Canary Islands. Challenges and Opportunities* was organised on 25th October 2022. The primary objective of the event was to facilitate a comprehensive discussion on the potential, prospects, and challenges of offshore energy in the Canary Islands, specifically with the local fishery communities. Additionally, the event served as an opportunity to introduce the recently launched AquaWind project and distribute the WP1 survey to gather valuable feedback and perceptions from stakeholders. The event aimed to establish a collaborative and inclusive approach to offshore energy development in the region by interacting with local fisheries communities.

2.8 Synergies with other projects/initiatives

EMFAF FLORA project

AquaWind has successfully established a collaboration channel with the **sister project FLORA** (<https://wedgeglobal.com/projects/>). FLORA technology, developed by Wedge Global, aims to optimise and validate a multisensory ocean station prototype that generates energy to support its oceanographic data services. Similar to AquaWind's W2Power prototype, the FLORA system undergoes real-sea testing at the PLOCAN test site for several months, aligning with the objectives of the Atlantic Maritime Strategy to promote marine renewable energies and sustainable growth of the blue economy in the Atlantic region.

The FLORA project is particularly interesting since like AquaWind it will perform its testing activities in the Atlantic Ocean and particularly in the same test site area at PLOCAN, Gran Canaria. This is interesting as synergies for data collection and sharing can be evaluated.

To forge this mutual collaboration, a first hybrid **joint event** was organised by AquaWind at the premises of CMC on **1st June 2023** and attended by both project consortium members. An additional online technical meeting has also been held later on to continue discussions on the potential collaborations. During these exchanges, the following potential synergies have been detected:

- 🌊 **Technical synergies:** It is likely that the pilot tests of the two projects might overlap for few weeks in late spring of 2024. Synergies in terms of data collection and sharing among the two projects that have been detected include: bird data, temperature, salinity, and underwater sound (FLORA will install a hydrophone). It has been discussed that a communication system to connect the two prototypes may be envisaged. It was concluded that in early 2024 the two projects will discuss again the technical aspects to understand the progress made by each of them and finally agree which collaborations in terms of sensors and data exchange can be eventually confirmed.
- 🌊 **D&C and exploitation synergies:** It was agreed to promote a joint webinar in May 2024 and to look for potential events in 2024 to be able to attend together. In addition, AquaWind committed to feature FLORA project through its newsletter and digital media. Collaboration will be also sought for the drafting of the policy briefs and business plan and exploitation strategy's development.

Contacts and information exchanges will continue, especially in early 2024 in order to evaluate the feasibility of shared dissemination and technical initiatives.

Figure 14. AquaWind – FLORA consortia

EU Missions - Restore our ocean and waters

As part of synergy building at the start of the project, WP7 Leader CE has engaged with the EU Missions - Restore our ocean and waters to feature AquaWind via a dedicated poster at the event of the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters Charter.

PLANASER 2.0 project

The **PLANASER 2.0** is a Spanish project funded by the Spanish Ministry of the Environmental Affairs, and Rural and Marine Affairs. PLANASER 2.0 was identified in the D&C Plan as one of the potential similar projects for synergies' creation with AquaWind, also considering that the ECOAQUA Institute of the ULPGC is engaged in both projects.

The main objective of the PLANASER 2.0 is to consolidate the cultivation of *Seriola* (*S. dumerili*) in Spain and position the country as a benchmark in the cultivation of this species through the innovations that are developed, promoting public-private cooperation and the transfer of knowledge to society.

Seriola species will be also used by AquaWind in its last pilot trial which aims to test and assess the feasibility of the *Seriola* production in offshore systems. PLANASER 2.0 will end this October 2023 and its results and advancements on experimental activities on *Seriola* can be relevant for future AquaWind pilot tests.

Beyond research-based synergies, PLANASER 2.0 and AquaWind have mutually supported each other through dissemination activities on social media and website, and AquaWind partners have been invited to join the PLANASER 2.0 Final Event scheduled on 5th October 2023.

2.9 Open-access

AquaWind is dedicated to upholding the principles and practices of Open Science and Open Access throughout the entire duration of the project, from its initiation to its completion. This commitment entails depositing public data generated by AquaWind into reputable open-access repositories, in accordance with the guidelines set forth by EMFAF as well as by the Horizon Europe (HE) programme on open access and utilising open licenses.

Placed on AquaWind's website, a "Results" section guarantees that all approved public deliverables by the EU are published and accessible for stakeholders throughout the project's lifespan. This section serves as a valuable resource for stakeholders to stay updated on the progress, findings, and outcomes of the AQUAWIND project. The section

also includes produced dissemination material ready to be downloaded, as well as gives promotion to the developed project videos.

In addition, the project is making use of Zenodo platform to share its findings, data and other outputs. Zenodo is a digital repository that offers researchers, scientists, and scholars a platform to openly share and preserve their research outputs, including datasets, software, images, videos, deliverables, and other publications. Operated by CERN and supported by funding from the European Commission, Zenodo guarantees its long-term sustainability and preservation.

A [Zenodo Community for AquaWind](#) has been created, and approved public deliverables have been uploaded to the platform. This community will be used for the dissemination of other open-access and non-confidential data and publications that will be produced by the consortium in the next two years of the project.

3. Monitoring and evaluation of dissemination activities

Within the framework of WP7, task 7.5 deals with the monitoring and evaluation of D&C activities. These are being monitored to ensure they are properly implemented and support the maximisation of the project's expected impacts. Monitoring of the activities allows to assess if the actions planned are carried out properly and on time and to measure their effectiveness. Based on monitoring results, the project D&C Plan might be thus reformulated to improve the communication and dissemination outreach.

To monitor the project, partners are periodically requested to provide information on the activities carried out (for instance organisation of events, publications of news/press releases, etc., presentations at conferences) while CE is in charge of monitoring and reporting on the use of the website, social media, and on the events whose organisation is under CE's responsibility. Based on the reports submitted from the partners, CE can formulate recommendations for the future dissemination and communication activities.

A continuous monitoring of the dissemination activities made by project partners is carried out within WP7 tasks. An internal file shared among partners keeps records of the press releases, articles, and events, gathering the information based on:

- The partner who carried out the activity.
- The date which the activity took place in.
- Activity outreach.
- Publication source.
- URL link to the activity results or proof.
- Targeted audience.
- In case of an event, the type of event, location, and general information.

Indicators' monitoring

In conjunction with the monitoring, an evaluation of the effectiveness of the activities will be performed periodically mainly using a set of target indicators of success set in the Grant Agreement and reported in the table below. The continuous monitoring will allow CE to assess the evolution and impacts of the dissemination and communication activities and evaluate any corrections or preventive measures to increase the reach-out of WP7 activities.

Table 11. Monitoring and evaluation indicators' progress at M12

Indicator	Target as per GA	Indicator progress at M12	Level of completion*
Participation of national/EU events	6	7	117%
Organisation of international conference	1 (with 80 attendants)	0	0% (to be organised at project end)
Production of newsletter	6	1	17%
Newsletter subscribers	148	155	105%
Nº of interviews	9 (3/year)	3	33%
Nº of press releases	9	36	400%
Website visits per month	227	~152	67%
Nº of peer reviewed publications	3	0	0%
Total followers (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, YouTube)	1000	926	92%
Nº of videos produced	3	1	33%
Nº of webinars/events	4 (2 for civil society organisations; 2 for policy makers)	1 (face-to-face event for civil society & fishery communities)	25%

- * Not started yet
- * Ongoing / on track
- * Already achieved or even overpassed

Overall, the monitoring of indicators set in the GA shows a good start of D&C actions for AquaWind and positive response from the European and local communities. As shown in the table above, several indicators are in progress also considering that the project activities started only one year ago, and two more years are left. For some indicators such as event attendance, No of press release, No of followers, etc the project has managed not only to attain but also to overpass such indicators demonstrating the efforts implemented by the consortium and the high interest created around the project so far. The project has not started to work yet on one indicator, that is the peer reviewed publications since the technical activities on the W2Power prototype are still at their early stage.

Conclusions

This report outlines the D&C activities that have taken place over the first twelve months of the AquaWind project. Following the strategy that had been initially set up in the AquaWind Dissemination and Communication Plan (D7.1), the WP7 leader, in collaboration with all partners, has worked on both the set-up and launch of the communication and dissemination tools & and the implementation of the different activities linked to them.

Each communication and dissemination action has fulfilled a specific goal and, therefore, targeted specific project stakeholders. The use of various communication tools, such as leaflets, roll-up and tailored templates, has allowed a cohesive visual identity and message to be presented to the target audience.

On the other hand, the project's website, social media channels, the events, and the distribution of newsletters have successfully ensured that stakeholders stay informed about project developments, while press releases have generated media coverage and increased the project's visibility.

Also, partnerships and synergies with complementary initiatives and sister projects have been established, helping the promotion of AquaWind and engagement of stakeholders.

In conclusion, D&C actions are on track and the next phase of WP7 actions will be devoted at improving the results obtained so far while focusing on the promotion of more technical activities related to the AquaWind prototype, which by then will be achieved and finalised.

